

Prosthetically Guided Emergence Profile Using Immediate Implant, Custom Provisional, and Modified Impression Coping: A Case-Based Approach

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Abstract

Aim and Background:

Restoring the esthetic zone with dental implants presents clinical challenges, particularly in preserving peri-implant soft tissue architecture and achieving a natural emergence profile. The emergence profile, defined as the contour of the restoration through the soft tissue, is critical for long-term esthetics, function, and hygiene. This report highlights a prosthetically driven implant placement approach using socket-shield technique, immediate temporization, and customized impression coping to achieve optimal esthetic outcomes.

Case Description:

A 28-year-old female presented with a fractured maxillary left central incisor. Intraoral examination and CBCT revealed a deficient buccal cortical plate. A socket-shield technique was planned to preserve the facial bone. Using the Partial Extraction Therapy (PET) kit, the buccal root segment was retained and shaped. Implant placement was performed in a prosthetically driven position, followed by immediate temporization with a screw-retained composite resin crown. After soft tissue maturation, the developed emergence profile was transferred using a customized impression coping fabricated from the provisional restoration template. A definitive screw-retained prosthesis was delivered, replicating the matured soft tissue contour and demonstrating harmonious esthetics and functional integration.

Conclusion:

The technique of socket-shield combined with immediate provisionalization and customized impression coping enables predictable soft tissue sculpting and emergence profile replication. This minimally invasive approach supports peri-implant health, reduces surgical interventions, and yields esthetically pleasing outcomes in anterior implant restorations.

Keywords:

Emergence Profile, Socket Shield, Immediate Temporization, Customized Impression Coping, Anterior Implant, Provisional Restoration, Esthetic Implant Dentistry, Prosthetically Driven Implant Placement

CASE REPORT

Introduction:

Dental implant therapy is a reliable solution for replacing missing teeth, especially in the esthetic zone. While early implantology followed a bone-driven approach—prioritizing implant placement based on available bone—this often compromised the ideal restorative position and esthetic outcome. A key factor in long-term success is the emergence profile, defined as the contour of the restoration as it traverses the soft tissue. An anatomically appropriate emergence profile enhances esthetics, maintains peri-implant health, and supports effective hygiene.

For implant restorations to be both esthetically pleasing and functionally successful, the soft tissue contours should harmonize with adjacent natural teeth [1]. The term “emergence profile” was first introduced by Stein and Kuwata in 1977 to describe the morphology of crowns as they transition through the gingival tissues toward the interproximal contact and buccolingual height of contour [2]. Croll’s photographic analysis further indicated that natural teeth typically exhibit a straight emergence profile rather than a concave or convex one [3].

Advancements in bone grafting materials, guided bone regeneration (GBR) techniques, and improved surface modifications of implants have led to a paradigm shift toward the “restoration-driven implant placement” concept [4]. This modern approach focuses on prosthetically ideal implant positioning, guided by the desired final restoration rather than bone availability alone, thereby improving esthetic predictability and peri-implant soft tissue health.

A critical factor in achieving esthetic integration, especially in the anterior maxilla, is the development of a natural and well-contoured emergence profile. The emergence profile—the contour of the crown as it exits the soft tissue—must closely mimic that of the natural tooth [5,6]. Poorly designed restorations can hinder oral hygiene access and contribute to soft tissue inflammation, negatively impacting the overall esthetic result [7]. Therefore, creating a harmonious and properly contoured emergence profile that aligns with adjacent teeth is essential for both function and appearance [8].

To sculpt an ideal emergence profile around implants, interim restorations can be progressively modified using a technique known as dynamic compression, which gradually conditions the soft tissue [9]. Achieving this ideal profile depends on multiple considerations throughout the treatment process, including implant selection, appropriate use of healing abutments, and provisional restorations. This report presents a case where gingival recontouring was achieved through provisional restoration, enabling the ideal emergence profile for the definitive implant restoration.

CASE DESCRIPTION:

A 28-year-old healthy female patient presented with a fractured maxillary left central incisor (tooth 21). Intraoral evaluation revealed a fractured maxillary central incisor (Figure 1). A cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) scan was performed to assess the alveolar ridge morphology, proximity to vital structures, and overall suitability for prosthetically driven implant placement. On Radiographic evaluation thin labial cortical plate was observed. With the objective of preserving the thin labial cortical plate and achieving optimal esthetics, a socket-shield approach was planned. (Figure 2)

Figure 1: Preoperative frontal view of the maxilla showing fractured central incisor

Figure 2: Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) scan showing thin labial cortical plate and socket shield planning and implant placement.

The root fragment was sectioned, and the buccal portion was carefully retained and shaped using the Partial Extraction Therapy (PET) kit, ensuring preservation of the periodontal ligament and socket integrity. (Figure 3&4)

Figure 3&4: Surgical preparation of the partial root segment (socket shield) and extracted palatal root fragment

Following shield preparation, implant osteotomy and placement were performed in a prosthetically favorable position, guided by the anticipated final restoration. (Figure 5) An immediate screw-retained temporary restoration was delivered to maintain soft tissue contour and emergence profile. (Figure 6&7)

Figure 5: Insertion of implant in a prosthetically driven position palatal to the prepared shield

Figure 6&7 : Immediate temporization with a screw-retained PMMA relined composite resin crown placed over a temporary abutment.

After adequate healing and tissue maturation, a customized impression coping was fabricated using a template derived from the contour of the provisional crown. (Figure 7) This technique ensured precise transfer of the peri-implant soft tissue architecture.

After the healing phase, the peri-implant soft tissue exhibited healthy contouring around the interim restoration. The provisional crown played a critical role in shaping the gingiva through controlled pressure and progressive modifications. This guided tissue adaptation led to the formation of a natural, concave emergence profile that mimicked adjacent teeth. The well-developed soft tissue architecture provided an ideal foundation for the final prosthesis seamlessly blended both functionally and esthetically with the surrounding dentition. (Figure 8 &9) After adequate healing and tissue maturation, a customized impression coping was fabricated using a

template derived from the contour of the provisional crown. (Figure10) This technique ensured precise transfer of the peri-implant soft tissue architecture.

Figure 8&9 : intraoral view showing harmonious gingival contour and natural emergence profile

Figure 10& 11 :Customized impression coping fabricated using the template created from the interim restoration and final impression made.

A definitive impression was made, and a final prosthesis was fabricated and delivered, replicating the established emergence profile and achieving optimal esthetic and functional outcomes. (Figure11) The use of a customized impression coping allowed accurate transfer of the peri-implant soft tissue contour, ensuring seamless integration with the surrounding dentition. The final prosthesis demonstrated excellent gingival harmony, stability, and patient satisfaction, validating the effectiveness of the prosthetically driven socket-shield protocol in anterior implant rehabilitation. (Figure12)

Figure 12: Post-operative intraoral view showing harmonious gingival contour and natural emergence profile of the final restoration.

DISCUSSION:

Achieving optimal esthetic outcomes with dental implants in the maxillary anterior region presents unique challenges, primarily due to the anatomical constraints related to bone volume, bone quality, and the preservation of the inter-dental papilla [10]. Immediate implant loading offers several advantages, including reduced treatment time, elimination of a second-stage surgical procedure, early restoration of function and esthetics, and psychological benefits for the patient [11].

An appropriately contoured emergence profile is essential for supporting the peri-implant soft tissues and maintaining effective oral hygiene [12]. Provisional restorations play a pivotal role in shaping the peri-implant gingival architecture during the healing phase and guiding the final esthetic outcome [13]. Multiple techniques have been described to sculpt soft tissues, develop emergence profiles, and accurately transfer these contours to the final prosthesis. Neale and Chee advocated for soft tissue recontouring using gingivoplasty prior to provisionalization [5],

whereas Ormianer et al. proposed the immediate placement of autopolymerizing acrylic resin into the sulcus to replicate tissue form [14]. However, intraoral manipulation of acrylic resin carries risks of chemical and thermal irritation to the soft tissues.

Hinds et al. later described a more tissue-friendly approach involving customized impression copings to accurately replicate the developed emergence profile after healing [15]. The technique presented in this article aligns with this concept by avoiding direct intraoral use of monomer-based materials, thereby reducing gingival irritation. Moreover, by gradually guiding tissue contouring with the provisional restoration during healing, this method often eliminates the need for second-stage surgery. Additionally, the use of a customized impression coping ensures precise transfer of the matured peri-implant soft tissue morphology, improving the accuracy and esthetics of the definitive restoration.

CONCLUSION :

The development and precise transfer of an ideal emergence profile are critical for achieving optimal esthetic and functional outcomes in implant-supported restorations, particularly in the anterior maxilla. The technique described—using a screw-retained immediate provisional restoration followed by a customized impression coping—offers a predictable and minimally invasive approach for guiding soft tissue healing and accurately replicating peri-implant contours. By eliminating the need for intraoral resin manipulation and second-stage surgeries, this method enhances patient comfort while preserving tissue health. The resulting final prosthesis demonstrates improved esthetics, soft tissue harmony, and hygiene accessibility, highlighting the clinical value of prosthetically driven implant placement combined with soft tissue conditioning protocols.

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